

Design Follows Personality

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Abstract

This paper is about a work model in which the company personality is the leading factor in the design process and has a major influence on how we perceive the products developed by a company, and which emotions it will evoke.

In design practice you are confronted with clients who, consciously or not, operate on the basis of their own characteristics. These can be separated into the product or service being marketed (behaviour), the way they speak to the consumers (communication) and the cultural values on the basis of which the company operates (symbols). Together, these three elements form the personality of the company, which is usually laid down in a mission statement and brand values. They represent the company's genetic material. The emotions evoked by the products, made and developed by the client, can be derived from these company genes. The bandwidth and elasticity of what the company can achieve is limited by these elements, not only instrumentally (the product or service marketed) but especially in terms of communication and the cultural values the company stands for. And the bandwidth of emotions their products can arouse is therefore also limited. After all, major variations in these matters create implausibility in the consumer's mind. Unambiguous development of the corporate personality is crucially important.

In everyday design practice, the model presented has proven to bring about a match between a company's strategy and user concerns, a match of personalities. Such a match ultimately results in a fulfilment of the concerns of the consumer and economic fulfilment on the part of the company. The paper will illustrate the practical value of this work model by means of a successful design case.

Keywords: design practice, brand values, company personality, consumer concern

Energy and emotions

In 2001, Dutch design company Fabrique was asked to design an Internet café for Essent, one of Holland's biggest energy companies. Apart from energy, Essent delivers cable and Internet services. The main goals of the Internet café are to communicate the Essent brand and the fact that Essent does more than energy alone. The biggest problem is the fact that the most important product of the company is intangible and has no differentiators in comparison to its competitors. Essent is very much aware of the fact that they can't compete on a product level alone. Fabrique carried out an extensive analysis of the company personality of Essent and manners to translate this into form and function, because they believe that this is the only valid starting point in the design process. For the company personality of Essent the key words are: 'open', 'effective' and 'inspired', which significantly distinguishes it from its competitors. The designers came up with a very expressive design, in form as well as in colour (see www.fabrique.nl, section ruimtelijk / corporate identity for pictures in full colour). They decided on a single big piece of furniture in the room, a giant metal ribbon that

acts as both a table for the build-in Internet keyboards and a bench, to sit on and watch the large television screens. The ribbon is functional as well as symbolising one of the core business activities of the company: putting cables into the ground. The walls on the left and right are completely back-lit. They impose themselves on the room and almost make ‘energy’ tangible. Two large plasma TV screens are mounted on the right wall. A line from a poem is printed on the left back-lit wall, which translates as ‘distance only separates the bodies, not the minds’, written by Dutch philosopher Erasmus. This line was chosen because it reflects the power of communication through the web in a subtle way. The design of the café, which forms part of a conference centre, evokes emotions (surprise, and inspiration) that match the company’s personality. The open character of the design invites you to use the Internet terminals or the remote control of the television screens. All together this total experience is strongly related to the company personality.

Figure 1, The Essent Internet café

Work model

This paper is about a work model in which the company personality is the leading factor in the design process. In the past 3 decades, insights in ‘how to design’ have undergone a great many changes. In the late 70s and early 80s, the principle of ‘form follows function’ - already a legacy of the Bauhaus doctrine - was generally accepted and widely applied. As a reaction to this, various movements came into being which went in the opposite direction, including

the Memphis movement. These movements, which often featured extravert design characteristics, could be summarised under the title 'form follows emotion', without the term 'emotion' being explored in depth in this respect. In most cases, it effectively meant 'form follows me', or in other words an almost autonomous approach to design. Control of the design process on the basis of emotion was non-existent. In addition, many approaches to design focused on one single aspect of the product, depending on the interest. It is hardly surprising that 'form follows trends' has become fairly well established in the fashion world. However, a strong focus does not provide a handle on the non-focused factors, which definitely are important in the design process. The only correct approach is therefore an integrated one, in which the various perception-related aspects are incorporated coherently in the design process.

Company genes

In the mid 80s, awareness was growing within the industry that control on the basis of design could lead to excellent results. Companies such as Apple had demonstrated this. At the same time, the existing methods and models offered little guidance in terms of establishing an individual, suitable and therefore usually distinctive design policy. It was also remarkable that the tendency towards conscious control on the basis of design aspects remained limited to industrial and graphic design. Architects, advertising companies and fashion designers, for example, all applied their own methods of steering in the design process.

A great deal changed in the 90s, particularly from an industry point of view. Nowadays the world has become transparent, and more than ever, new technologies have become universally available. In the 20th century, an advantage over one's competitors could be obtained through exclusivity in the distribution channels, technology or the protection of know-how. The new world, borne aloft by high technology, quickly brought an end to these advantages.

From the research field, a great deal was written and talked about the perception of a product by the user. From the point of view of the design practice, there was a strange aspect to this. Never before had users been knocking on the doors of designers or design firms, asking them to design something for them. Users who told them what they wanted and how much they wanted to pay for it. Of course you can use consumer research to find out more about what

the customer wants, although this usually neither reveals much about their latent needs, nor take into account what the company can produce or supply.

Instead of this, we designers now have daily contact with companies which present us with design problems. Through the years, however, I have become aware that the number of possible design results on the basis of a design problem is far smaller than you might think. In particular, the culture, history and drive of a company are determinative for the nature of the product that the company wants to and can produce and/or market. These factors can be regarded as 'the company's genes' and they play an important role in the design process, albeit often in the background. Increasingly, instrumental limitations have almost no effect in this respect. In the past, one might have been limited by the machinery or distribution system at one's disposal. These days, a large number of products - from peanut butter to bicycles to MP3 players - can be bought as finished items in accordance with previously issued specifications. How is one company able to make a success of a product, while another company is not? Over the years, I have become convinced that successful companies have strong genetic material, which is often expressed as a decisive common awareness of where the company wants to go, what motivates the people and what binds them together. In fact a company acts like a living organism with 'genes' that tell you something about the potential, but also about the limitations of what the company is able to. It is often the case that strong individuals have formed the basis for this type of company, such as Richard Branson (Virgin), Steve Jobs (Apple), the Freitag brothers (Freitag) or Stelios Haji (Easy Jet). And it is this drive that is often so recognisable and attractive to the outside world, because it is pure, often averse to conventions, and therefore distinguishes itself in a natural manner. This drive is reflected in the products or services, these companies offer. They often achieve a natural brand equity, a situation that many companies are striving towards. In this pioneer's phase of these types of rebel brands, designers often play a stimulating and important role. For example, in the 1980s, Frog Design was chosen to translate Steve Jobs' ideas into an attractively designed computer, the first Apple Macintosh. In the 1980s, the young graphic designer Peter Saville managed to translate the wild ideas of entertainment entrepreneur Tony Wilson (Factory Records) into outstanding designs, which made a vital contribution to the perception and credibility of the label. So outstanding, in fact, that the sleeves were often better than the music.

During the pioneer's phase, in particular, entrepreneurial intuition plays a very large role. The combination of product, communication and attitude created what was later recognised as a strong brand. All of the companies referred to above went through a rebellious phase at some point, lead by intuition. In order to stay on course, it is important that companies identify their drivers at a certain point. Even if this is only to assist in internal communication. In practice, these drivers or core values - there are a great many terms used for what is in effect the same concept - act as excellent input for design processes. Together they form the company personality. It is important to realise that the bandwidth and elasticity of what the company can achieve is limited by the company personality, especially in terms of the cultural values the company stands for (Franzen and Van den Berg, 2002).

Company Personality

All the above reveals something of the complexity involved in mapping out a company personality. Less than 15 years ago, designers were asked to create a design for a product. We were asked to get involved with the intrinsic qualities of the products. These product qualities form part of the total experience. Separate from this, the 'soft values' are playing an increasingly large role in the experience of the product, such as the stories which generally adhere to a product, and which are reflected in the brand. These stories are usually carried by advertising and/or public relations.

Birkigt and Stadler (1986) developed a model, which was originally intended as a tool for denoting the discrepancy between identity and image. They based their theory on the fact that everything a company does is anchored in the company personality, which is usually expressed in core values. A derivative version of the model (see Figure 2) shows that the company personality is expressed through three different channels: symbols, communication and behaviour. These three channels act in their own way and evoke emotions.

Figure 2, Company personality model

Symbols stand for the representation of the deeper values for which the company stands. These often focus on subconscious emotions. Behaviour is usually instrumental, resulting in a perception of the product with which the commercial actions of the company take place. Generally speaking, this is a very strong interaction component. Communication stands for the way in which contact is maintained with all the internal and external interested parties. It is often explicitly oriented towards stories around the product that evoke emotions. One major objection to design philosophies is that they are strongly oriented towards the development of the form only. In this model, the form is a part of the total experience. A place is given to all the aspects which influence the experience of the consumer, most of which are often brand related. As said, designers usually deal with the intrinsic product characteristics. In most cases, these are not the only distinguishing factors which determine the difference between success and failure, for the simple reason that it is often very difficult to distinguish oneself with intrinsic product features.

On the basis of the model in Figure 3, the theory that products of the company are made up of the same genetic material is not so complicated. Products and services are a reflection of the corporate personality. Obviously, the mix of characteristics will vary, depending on the purpose of the product or service, and the context. As will be clear, all expressions of the company contribute to the total perception.

Generally we understand the term product or service to mean something that is commercially traded. Other elements, such as the packaging, advertising, retail outlets, a website and forms

of customer contact can also be regarded as products of the company, and contribute to the perception (Figure 3).

Figure 3, Products as a reflection of the company personality

As I have mentioned, the personality of the company acts as a starting point. It is expressed in the personality characteristics. Although the behaviour channel is more or less the territory of the product designer, the symbols channel the territory of the corporate identity designer and the communication channel that of the advertising company, all products will contain ingredients of all three. It is the role of the designer to decide if, how and in which channel a personality characteristic should be expressed. In the 80s, the design of Volvo cars was very square, in order to express one the core values of the company: safety. This was done for symbolic reasons, and not because it was necessary for intrinsic safety reasons. In every product a different mix is made (Figure 4), depending on the goals. In this way, design follows personality.

Figure 4, Different products, different mixes of characteristics

This is simple enough on paper. In practice, however, it is difficult for companies to control every aspect on the basis of a homogeneous philosophy. Bearing in mind that ‘communication’ is often the territory of advertisers, ‘symbolism’ the territory of corporate identity designers and the product is developed by product developers, experience shows that the interests are often not synchronised. Strong entrepreneurship is therefore needed in order to be able to control the design process in this way. An integrated and centrally directed approach is necessary in order to do a better job than your competitors, or in any case to create a distinctive image for yourself.

The consumer

The design-follows-personality approach is bottom-up orientated. But we cannot give substance to the design process without gaining insight into the interests of the consumer. Many people have already demonstrated that the general perception of product emotions goes beyond colour and form. Stories play an important role. Each aspect of the product, whether interaction, price, packaging or brand, contributes to the total perception. A work model would therefore have to offer insights into how to control on the basis of this total perception. And in particular the total experience of the user.

The consumer, user or viewer -who for the sake of convenience I will refer to from now on as the consumer - tests his assessment against his concerns. These concerns are context-dependent and can therefore vary greatly. Roughly speaking, we can distinguish three types of concerns: goals, attitudes and standards (Desmet, 2002). Depending on this consideration, emotions will be generated, with the product acting as a stimulus. The tendency to act on the basis of the confrontation with the product will be dependent on this confrontation. In other

words, an interaction takes place which can have an extremely diverse nature (see Figure 5). The concerns represent a part of the consumer's personality. The consumer identifies his personality with that of the product and forms an opinion on the basis of this, and in some particular case he may wish to purchase the product or interact with the product. Many aspects play a role in this. The facets which he considers to be relative with respect to other products (can I purchase something which appeals more to my interests?), may at any moment be subject to change and, despite an attractive product, his actions may be economically limited. The interaction between consumer and product can be seen as an evaluation by the consumer, in which he/she weighs up the emotions the product evokes against his/her own concerns.

The role of the designer

The designer can play an important role in the process of identification between consumer and product. Initially he can participate in the determination of which personality characteristics are most suitable to be expressed in the product to design. In this way he can take part in the process to balance the way the company is expressing itself. The work model is also a suitable platform for dialogue between all the parties that are responsible for looking at the consumer; the designer is the person who has to make a match between the personalities of the consumer and the product.

Figure 5, the designer takes care of the match between the personalities

Practice

In practice, there are many examples of good matches between company personality and consumer personality. Apple's Steve Jobs has one motto in his life: 'to make a difference'. Taking this core proposition as a basis, control can be exercised over product development, packaging, advertising and PR. It is therefore hardly surprising that Apple led the field for decades in the area of PC innovation. It is getting increasingly difficult for Apple, however: while a head start could be held onto for around 10 years in 1984, these days it is barely 6 months. This was the period between the first iPod appearing on the market and the first clones appearing. 'Make the difference' is a personal characteristic with which Apple users are happy to identify themselves, consciously or unconsciously.

The work model also shows why, as a company, you should not always be happy that certain groups identify themselves with you, even though your market share is growing. There are plenty of examples of products which have been embraced by football hooligans, for example. The most well-known example is the popularity of the Lonsdale brand among neo-Nazis. Under a half-open jacket you can see the letters NSDA, a reference to Hitler's NSDAP. By wearing it in this way, significance is added to the product which was not originally intended.

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